

**CHARACTERISTICS OF DEVELOPING EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN
INVESTMENT MANAGEMENT IN BUSINESS ACTIVITY**

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Abstract: *This article examines the creation of an investment climate, the level of emotional intelligence of entrepreneurs, the ability to understand human emotions, understand the intentions, motives and desires of others and themselves, as well as solving practical problems.*

Key words: *Entrepreneurship, investment, intelligence, ability, problem, environment, development..*

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Our economy is developing more and more today. In the implementation of the goal of improving the investment environment in accordance with the third part of the Strategy of Actions adopted for the political, economic, cultural and educational development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, it helps to create jobs by attracting direct foreign investments. Formation and development of the investment environment is planned to be implemented on the basis of two components.

1- component: Strengthening the legal and regulatory framework aimed at attracting foreign investments, attracting investments and protecting the rights of investors. Also, developing economic liberalization scenarios and analyzing their impact on different segments of the population, developing their own proposals for reducing negative impacts.

2- component: raising the professional skills of members of parliament and specialists of ministries and agencies in the field of investment, as well as raising general awareness of the reforms being implemented in this area. There are several types of investment: state, foreign, private and citizen investments. Investment is divided into two forms: financial and real. In the financial form, it is the purchase of bonds, shares and similar securities, while in the real form, it is done by investing in activities such as material production, industry, and construction. Nowadays, the third intellectual form is also developing. This includes licenses, collaborative research.

The export-import national insurance company "Uzbekinvest" established in 1994 operates in the field of insurance of foreign investments in Uzbekistan. Investment plays a major role in the development of a country's economy. In the classical

economic model, savings and investment are equated with indicators such as profit and consumption. It is appropriate to carry out this task by entrepreneurs and representatives of the business community. An entrepreneur is a risk-taker who undertakes to realize bold, important and complex goals and takes full responsibility for the implementation of new ideas. In the economic development of today's society, the entrepreneur is tasked with constantly improving his knowledge and professional skills, expanding the field of communication and information. Due to the development of new trends and crisis situations, the individual is required to take responsibility for studying the business environment and the field of interpersonal relations. One of the main problems is to increase the effectiveness of a person's activity in society and in his life as a whole. From this point of view, it is necessary to develop the ability to regulate one's own behavior, interaction with the environment, to overcome life tasks and difficulties. In entrepreneurs, this ability is determined by their level of emotional intelligence. "Emotional intelligence" is the ability to understand human emotions, to understand the intentions, motives and desires of others and oneself, as well as the ability to perceive and manage the emotions of other people in order to solve practical problems. The study of the problem of "emotional intelligence" is of great interest for business activities, because in the modern developing society there is strong competition, emotional intelligence can be the main source of company development. First of all, it concerns people who are directly related to business, that is, entrepreneurs. Emotional intelligence directly applies to any activity related to communicating with people. With this in mind, the development of emotional intelligence in entrepreneurs is the basis for the development of the market economy and the investment environment. There are several models of developing "Emotional Intelligence", one of which is the "Emotional Intelligence" model by Peter Salovey and John Meier in 1990. In the field of psychology, this model is currently the main one.

Maer, Salovey and Caruso distinguish four components of emotional intelligence as follows:

1. Understanding emotions - the ability to understand the emotions of other people (facial expressions, gestures, appearance, gait, behavior, voice), as well as to identify one's own emotions. An important factor in managing the investment environment in cooperation with foreign investments in business activities is the development of the ability to understand emotions. Management of partners and investors by facial expressions, gestures, appearance, walking, behavior, and activities makes the entrepreneur comfortable.
2. The use of emotions that stimulate thinking is the ability of a person to activate the thinking process (mostly unconsciously), to awaken creativity in them, to use emotions as a stimulating tool. taught self-control with encouragement.
3. Understanding emotions - the ability to determine the cause of an emotion, to know the relationship between thoughts and emotions, to determine the transition from one

emotion to another, to predict the development of emotions in time, as well as to interpret emotions in relationships, to understand complex (ambiguous, ambiguous) emotions. Management of business activities requires responsibility. is enough. In this process, understanding the relationship between thoughts and emotions moderates the psychological climate in relations with customers and colleagues. In business activity, it is necessary to move from one emotion to another at the same time. If the ability to understand one's feelings is developed, the level of conflict situations will decrease.

4. Emotional management is the ability to evoke and manage one's own emotions and the emotions of others in order to achieve one's goals. It also includes the ability to take into account emotions when making logical chains, solving various problems, making decisions and choosing behavior. It serves to solve various problems of entrepreneurs through the emotion management component. In managing the investment environment, it provides comfort for individuals with a high level of emotional intelligence. With its help, emotionally developed people find it much easier to connect with others. This situation is of urgent importance for business circles. People with a high level of emotional intelligence are constantly changing and adapting to the situation. Rather than fearing change, waits for them and thinks ahead about their actions. Emotional intelligence also means self-control. In conclusion, it should be noted that the investment environment in the market economy is developed and managed through external and internal relations. In this field, increasing the level of emotional intelligence of entrepreneurs serves as a factor determining the effectiveness of activity.

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